

Conformity report of IPBES assessments with the data and knowledge management policy;

→ Transformative Change Assessment

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Highlights

- The overall score of the Transformative Change assessment was 82.9%
- Good compliance of most of the criteria, but room for improvement on the delivery of figures and tables.
- Based on the conclusions of the conformity reports for the IAS Assessment and this assessment, the technical support unit for data and knowledge management suggests adjusting the scoring methodology for criteria related to bibliographic references.

Rationale

Compliance with the IPBES data and knowledge management policy (DKMP) and the delivery protocol for assessment is essential to assess the quality of IPBES assessment reports and to evaluate the effectiveness of the task force on data and knowledge management. To support this evaluation, the technical support unit for data and knowledge management developed a standardized protocol to produce conformity reports.

The first conformity reports using this protocol were conducted for the Values and Sustainable Use Assessments, which scored 72.4% and 69.2% respectively. Following the approval of the Invasive Alien Species Assessment, the same protocol was applied, resulting in a significantly higher conformity score of 93.2%.

At IPBES-11, conformity reports became a requirement for the task force of data and knowledge management, ensuring continuous monitoring of compliance over time. Therefore, the task force decided to continue the use of the protocol, to allow for an objective and comparable index of conformity.

In December 2024, the Transformative Change Assessment was approved at IPBES-11 and, after evaluation, obtained a conformity score of 82.9%. This conformity report provides valuable insights on how well the IPBES data and knowledge management policy is currently implemented in IPBES products, and it highlights areas where the delivery protocol for assessment drafts could be improved.

Introduction

The first IPBES data management policy was published in 2020, after being approved by the MEP and Bureau meeting in January of that year. To have a global impact, IPBES reports have to be transparent and trustworthy, and the policy sets out the requirements to achieve this. In order to give practical guidance, the IPBES delivery protocol of the assessment drafts was developed, which sets out to assist the technical support units of the assessments with the implementation of the policy in their milestone drafts. Both the policy and the delivery protocol are designed to be regularly updated, with the most recent revisions published in 2024 (data and knowledge management policy version 2.1: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3551078>; delivery protocol of the assessment drafts: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6225417>). The newest version of the delivery protocol provides information on all the steps and actions at every milestone, and includes a checklist that technical support units can use to ensure following the policy. Additionally, the technical support unit for data and knowledge management holds regular meetings with the technical support units for assessments to discuss any matters related to data and knowledge management and the DKMP, and several technical guidelines have been developed and published on the IPBES ICT Portal (<https://ict.ipbes.net/ipbes-ict-guide/data-management/technical-guidelines>), and kept

up to date, to support the IPBES experts and assessment technical support units with the implementation of the DKMP.

An objective scorecard was designed to 'score' each assessment on how well they complied to the delivery of the drafts protocol, and thereby to the data and knowledge management policy. The findings will give an insight into the performance of the assessments as well as show which (sub)sections of the policy and protocol are causing difficulties for the assessment TSUs. These conclusions will inform revisions of the policy and the delivery protocol, and provide information which technical guidelines could be developed to better inform and support the IPBES experts and assessment TUSs.

Here, the conformity of the Transformative Change Assessment with the DKMP is assessed. This assessment report was approved in December 2024 by the Plenary at IPBES-11.

Results

The results table is added at the end of this report.

Overall performance: The average score of all sections together determined the overall score, which in case of the Transformative Change Assessment was 82.7%. The number of citations in the reference list with an identifier has increased from the previous conformity report. The delivery of the figures and tables comply less with the DKMP than the Invasive Alien Species Assessment, and therefore requires more attention. The score of each of the subsections is broken down below:

Citation: The assessment scored 100% for the citations. The Transformative Change assessment is the first assessment for which the affiliation is added for all authors, including contributing authors (following the previous recommendation of using the [guideline on experts lists](#)). This enables the use of authors lists for any analyses on the nationalities, countries of residence and countries of affiliation of the authors affiliated in IPBES. To ensure that all information is accurate and complete, it is crucial that all country information is added by the authors directly.

Bibliographic references: The assessment scored 71.4% for the bibliographic references. The uncited references in the Zotero library were not yet all deleted. However, as all the cited references have tags which indicate in which chapter(s) the citation is cited, which facilitates the cleaning of the library. Not all references that we recited have an identifier; as not all entries in the bibliography have an identifier. In the assessment report (the five chapters, the Summary for Policymakers and the Glossary),

a total of 2262 references were cited. 1695 of the references have a doi (74.9% of all references), 357 references have an isbn number (15.8%), 1402 references have an ISSN number (62%) and 1887 have an url (83.4% of the whole library). Only 11 references have no identifier, which accounts for 0.5% of all cited references. As the uncited references are not deleted, there are 5 retracted references in the Zotero library, but none of these is cited in the assessment.

Chapters and supplementary material: The assessment scored 100% on the delivery of the chapters and supplementary material. Each chapter and accompanying materials, such as a Zenodo entry for the figures and tables, the data management reports, and the bib files including all references cited in the chapters, SPM and Glossary, are uploaded to Zenodo. Connections between uploads are made on Zenodo, to facilitate easy navigating between the documents. The references in the docx files are all linked to Zotero. Following the Invasive Alien Species Assessment, the translated versions of the Summary for Policymakers are uploaded to Zenodo in a way that makes the search for these translations easier, as the translated title is the title of the entry, whereas the description mentions in English that it is a translation of the Summary for Policymakers in a specific language.

Figures: The assessment scored 58.8% for the delivery of the figures. Because there were no country names used in the figures, this subsection (both for schematic and data driven figures) was excluded from the scoring. All the interoperable and final figures are uploaded to Zenodo. Official permission to use borrowed figures was requested and granted, and although citations (with a link to Zotero) were added in the caption, the licences under which these figures were initially published were not. Also, although most figures are original figures and few are borrowed, changes made to borrowed figures have not been described in the caption or in a DMR (for example 1.3 and 4.1 were adapted from the IPBES Global assessment). For photos, copyright and appropriate licences were included. Usage rights for original figures were not included in the captions, but are available on Zenodo. Against the policy, there are few world maps in the assessment, which are not presented in Robinson projection (SPM.11 and figure 4.7), and in figure 4.7 country borders are included. According to the policy, all generated maps should be presented in Robinson projection, as it balances the distortion and allows the projection of the world in one figure. Country borders are only allowed in borrowed figures, as country borders can change over time and are sometimes prone to political sensitivity.

Tables: The assessment scored 50% for the delivery of tables. The tables and captions were uploaded to Zenodo. There are some tables in the assessment (Table 1.3. Summary of actor types and actor groups, exemplified with initiatives from the case

study database; Table 4.1 Examples illustrating the challenges that diverse kinds of telecoupling pose to transformative change; Table 5.1 Overview of case studies in chapter 5 illustrating potential roles for four actor groups in implementing options that contribute to transformative change when combined with other options in context specific pathways; and Table 5.3 Ways of characterizing human-nature relationships in diverse cultures and languages) where the country names were written out instead of following the ISO 3166-1 alpha 3 code. The written out names do not always follow the country names as recommended by the United Nations, for example, it states the U.S. instead of the United States of America, Russia instead of the Russian Federation and Bolivia instead of the Plurinational State of Bolivia. No disclaimers and licences were necessary to be included in the table captions. The interoperable versions of the tables were added to Zenodo, but these were done in docx instead of csv. It is possible that this was chosen to keep the links to Zotero intact, but csv file formats are often easier to deal with in programs like R and Python (unless there are merged cells or other complexities). For the ongoing and upcoming assessments, it could be advised to upload tables in both formats.

Data and knowledge from Indigenous Peoples and local communities: All the requirements regarding data from Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities were fulfilled; the IPLCs were informed, gave their consent and approved the representation of their shared knowledge. The terms of agreement on reuse, representation and storage was documented and materials were uploaded to Zotero following these terms.

Disclaimers: The assessment fulfilled the requirements regarding the disclaimers; there is a general disclaimer for the full assessment, and a disclaimer for each individual chapter, which were checked and approved by the secretariat.

Discussion

Overall, the conformity score of the Transformative Change Assessment (82.9%) was satisfactorily high. Compared to the previous scored assessments, Transformative Change scored higher than the Values (72.4%) and Sustainable Use (69.2%) assessments, but not as high as the Invasive Alien Species assessment (93.2%). The delivery of tables and figures was near perfect for Invasive Alien Species, but not as complete for Transformative Change. For ongoing and upcoming assessments, more emphasis could be added to the delivery of tables and figures, for example through comments on the external reviews, but also in adhoc meetings dedicated to the tables and figures. This could make sure that the delivery of tables and figures will be done better in the future.

As the same scorecard was used for this assessment as for the previous conformity reports, the same discussion on the nuance of using a binary scoring metric applies. For the Invasive Alien Species Assessment, 1.4% of the references cited in the assessment did not have an identifier, which led to the suggestion that binary scoring can be too strict. For the Transformative Change assessment, the percentage of references without an identifier was 0.5%, which brings up the same discussion on the 'fairness' of binary scoring. For future conformity evaluations, when not all references, but at least 95% of the references have an identifier, this subsection should receive a score of 1 instead of 0.

One important observation from the references without an identifier that were cited in the report, is that out of only 11 incomplete references 2 are IPBES ILK dialogue workshop reports: the third ILK dialogue workshop for the Values Assessment and the third ILK dialogue workshop for the Transformative Change Assessment. A solution could be to upload the workshop reports to Zenodo, so that they can be added to Zotero using the doi, which would ensure that all metadata is automatically added to the library. Also, similar to the previous conformity reports, Transformative Change contained tables with written out country names instead of the ISO 3166-1 alpha 3 code. While written out country names could increase readability of the table, according to the delivery protocol, the ISO 3166-1 alpha 3 codes should be used. Possibly to avoid misinterpretations and for completeness, both the official written out names (as recommended by the United Nations) as well as the ISO 3166-1 alpha 3 codes could be included in tables.

Based on this report, the task force on knowledge and data asked the technical support unit for data to consider a maturity model, which classifies the different sections and subsections of the policy into different categories, ranging from 'essential' to 'good to have'. Such a model would allow for a deviation from the binary scoring, and gives weight to the most important sections. Some of the items on the scorecard require special attention and care from the assessment technical support units, such as the delivery of tables and figures, whereas other items are implied and require less or no additional work, such as the disclaimers which are added to each chapter, and the delivery of data and knowledge from Indigenous Peoples and local communities.

The choice to use the scorecard developed for an earlier version of the delivery protocol, was to be able to measure the progress that has been made. However, to be thorough, some aspects from the most recent version of the delivery protocol are discussed here. For example, the delivery protocol states that figures and tables should be uploaded before the Plenary, and access should be restricted, so that all information remains confidential until the assessment is approved by the Plenary. Uploading the

material before the Plenary allows users to access the metadata, and to add the correct identifier of the material to the citations. The technical support unit for the Transformative Change Assessment uploaded all entries to Zenodo in a restricted way, which allows access to the metadata, while keeping the actual materials confidential. Additionally, uploading materials in a restricted way ensures that searching the doi will yield a result instead of giving a 'not found' error. All entries on Zenodo were part of the IPBES community, which increases findability, and all authors are listed as authors with their ORCID. The review editors are added as 'contributors', and contributing authors are not included in the authors list on Zenodo. For each entry, the CC-BY 4.0 licence was added. Additionally, the Transformative Change Assessment was the first to use the new versioning scheme, making the distinction between different versions much easier to comprehend.

Methods

The previous version of the delivery protocol of the assessment drafts (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6225417>, version 1.2) includes nine different sections:

- Citations (the citations of the full report, individual chapters, SPM and the authors list)
- Bibliographic references
- Supplementary material
- Delivery of schematic figures
- Delivery of data driven figures
- Delivery of borrowed/adapted figures
- Delivery of tables
- Delivery of data and knowledge from Indigenous people and local communities
- Disclaimers

To avoid a bias towards the figures, the sections delineating the delivery of figures were scored together, so that 7 sections remained. For each subsection, it was evaluated whether the assessment complied with the requirements; and scored with a 1 if all elements of the subsection complied and scored with 0 if any element failed to comply. The total score of each section was transformed into a percentage, with a maximum score of 100%, after which the total score for the assessment was calculated as the average score of the different sections.

Scorecard for the Transformative Change Assessment

Description	Responsible Party	Binary	Count	Binary_sum	Score
Citations			5	5	100.0%
Suggested citation entire assessment	Assessment TSU	1			
Suggested citation SPM	Assessment TSU	1			
Suggested citation individual chapters	Assessment TSU	1			
Complete list of authors	Assessment TSU	1			
Citations and list approved by Secretariat	Secretariat	1			
Bibliographic references			5	7	71.4%
Library in Zotero	Secretariat	1			
Chapters in separate folders in Zotero	Secretariat	1			
All references cited entered in the right folder	Assessment TSU	1			
Unused references are deleted	Assessment TSU	0			
In-text citations complete and unbroken	Assessment TSU	1			
All entries have an identifier	Assessment TSU	0			
All references are in APA style	Assessment TSU	1			

Delivery of the chapters and supplementary materials			7	7	100.0%
Chapters in docx with connection to Zotero	Assessment TSU	1			
Chapters in pdf	Assessment TSU	1			
Exported bibliography (.bib)	Assessment TSU	1			
Authors' names in correct order	Assessment TSU	1			
Related identifier to SPM on Zenodo	Assessment TSU	1			
Related identifiers for DMR and data deposit packages	Assessment TSU	1			
Data management reports uploaded to Zenodo	Assessment TSU	1			
Delivery of figures			7	16	58.8%
Original format uploaded to Zenodo	Assessment TSU	1			
Interoperable and open format uploaded to Zenodo	Assessment TSU	1			
Native files provided to graphic designer to update colours	Assessment TSU	1			

Country borders in line with UN guidelines	Assessment TSU	-			
Usage rights (CCO or CC-BY) assigned	Assessment TSU	0			
Caption contains DOI and appropriate disclaimer if applicable	Assessment TSU	0			
Workflow/scripts used to create figure uploaded to Zenodo	Assessment TSU	1			
Native files provided to graphic designer to update colours	Assessment TSU	1			
Country borders in line with UN guidelines	Assessment TSU	0			
World maps in Robinson projection	Assessment TSU	0			
Country names in data follow the ISO 3166-1 alpha 3 code	Assessment TSU	-			
Usage rights (CCO or CC-BY) assigned	Assessment TSU	0			
Caption contains DOI and appropriate disclaimer if applicable	Assessment TSU	0			

Permission to reuse figure is granted from original authors or publisher	Assessment TSU	1			
Figure is reviewed	Assessment TSU	1			
High resolution copy uploaded to Zenodo	Assessment TSU	1			
Proper citation of the figure added to Zotero library	Assessment TSU	1			
Usage rights (CC0 or CC-BY) assigned	Assessment TSU	1			
Caption contains DOI and appropriate disclaimer if applicable	Assessment TSU	0			
Delivery of tables			1	2	50.0%
Original machine-readable data underlying the table along with caption uploaded to Zenodo	Assessment TSU	1			
Country names in data follow the ISO 3166-1 alpha 3 code	Assessment TSU	0			
Caption contains DOI and appropriate disclaimer if applicable	Assessment TSU	-			
Delivery of data and			4	4	100.0%

knowledge from Indigenous Peoples and local communities					
IPLCs are informed and consent	Assessment TSU	1			
IPLCs approve the representation of their shared knowledge	Assessment TSU	1			
Terms of agreement on reuse, representation and storage is documented	Assessment TSU	1			
Materials are uploaded to Zotero following the agreed terms	Assessment TSU	1			
Disclaimers			3	3	100.0%
Suggested general disclaimer	Assessment TSU	1			
Suggested disclaimers for maps, figures and tables are added to captions when necessary	Assessment TSU	1			
Suggested disclaimers are checked and approved by Secretariat	Secretariat	1			
				Final Score	82.9%